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Atonal Music Composition And The Performance In A Digital Era In Nigeria: Problems, Possibilities And Prospects

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ABSTRACT

A major hindrance to the composition and performance of Nigerian atonal art music is the difficulty in performing Nigerian music which lacks the gravitational pull of a tonal center. Although Nigerian music is basically tonal as well as her language, several traditional instrumental works of Nigerian music where the instruments used are not regulated and configured strictly to equal temperament or a unified tonal system, proves that Nigerian music can also tolerate musical sound that may not necessarily be guided strictly by tonality. The clashes in instrumental timbres accompanied with rhythmic sophistication is not a musical problem for the Nigerian musical ear. This paper advocates for the use of digital means as a way of mitigating the several challenges in composing and performing atonal music. However, the problems, possibilities, and prospects of such means are discussed in this study. Digital technology presents vast opportunities for self-expression which captures atonal music production, propagation and performance. This article encourages Nigerian atonal music composition and performance which have received lesser attention after the days of Uzoigwe, Akpabot and Sadoh.

Keywords: Atonal art music, tonality, atonality, Nigerian music

INTRODUCTION

Some people consider African music as largely tonal in the European equal temperament configuration. Little is said, heard, written or composed of atonal African music. This is due to several factors. Firstly, the colonialists concentrated on tonal music in their musical training of early Nigerian composers and performers.

Agawu (2011) along this line mentioned that:

Had the protestant hegemony been offset by exposure to, say, twentieth century music, including that of the European avant-garde (a tradition which, by definition, lies at a certain cutting edge), this tonal heritage would have taken a different form. A familiarity with so-called World Music would most certainly have affected the tonal imagination of composers. Claims about a new globalized musical economy may offer hope of equal access to the world's store of music in the future, but those who occupy the margins know better than to order their lives according to the promise of a dream. For now, we must contend with the fact that a largely protestant tonal legacy continues to dominate the musical consciousness of many budding composers. (p.55)

The constant performance and proliferation of tonal hymns, music for liturgical purposes and even popular music stood to strengthen the tonal legacy. While it is erroneous to say there is no tonality in

Nigerian music, it is also wrong to say African music is always in conformity to the European tonal system.

Melants, Cornelis and Leman (2009) stated that,

Pitch organisation in the music of Sub-Saharan Africa does not rely on a fixed theoretical framework. Ethnomusicological research has shown that a large variety of scales is in use. Often these scales use intervals that do not conform to the European chromatic scale, e.g. the use of intervals around 240 cents in (roughly) equidistant pentatonic scales

It is even possible that what we sing today as African songs have been adjusted to our new European tonal legacy. This thought is inspired by the fact that many of the African musical instruments used to accompany some of these songs which have been retained into our present century have separate tuning systems in which case they may not perfectly fit in chordal consideration with the songs to form what we may see as tonal structure from our European training. Some of them have microtonal, semitonal and timbral distinctions away from the sound region of the songs that they go with. To support this claim, an ethnomusicologist has gathered from field research that women constantly produce scales that defy natural diatonic expectations when judged with our European-trained ears. In the researched opera composition by Ngobili Chijioke, his experience with Ogidi (Anambra state) women was that they constantly produce of lowered seventh and sometimes third in the heptatonic scale on which their songs are built.

Agawu (2011) made it clear that:

The other side of the African composer's heritage comprises the African legacy in all its magnificent diversity. 'Africa' has to be understood in the broadest possible terms, and its influence may include actual materials, procedures, and performance practices. Acquiring the elements of this heritage would seem to follow a natural path for composers born into the tradition, but the process proves to be more complex. For some composers, the process of acquisition comes later in life when, quite self-consciously, they turn to the systematic study of traditional music in reaction to a lopsided educational system that rewards knowledge of Schumann and Brahms but not knowledge of Akan funeral dirges and Yoruba Dùndún drumming. (p.56)

This idea of getting a folk song and forcing it into a piano and European trained voices and ears, may not absolutely be a bad idea, but we are losing something we can save. Most times, Europeans consider our music more in the realm of rhythm. Melody and harmony in Nigerian music are also deep as well.

Uzoigwe and Atonality

Uzoigwe remains one of the few composers that have attempted to involve atonality in his African art compositions. He made it clear that one can deduce atonal music structures from African folk/traditional musical performances just like someone else would do in favour of tonal music. According to him, African art music is still struggling for a noble place on the global stage when compared to African literature (Uzoigwe, 2001:161). He has expressed that Afro-American music has succeeded in retaining African musical concepts while incorporating Western music practice. In his own words,

The concept of tonality and atonality, for the African Composer, therefore, should not be seen or interpreted in the same way Western Society sees and interprets them. For in African musical tradition, tonal centres often fluctuate even within a given musical composition, depending on the fluctuations in performance-situation and other non-musical factors (Uzoigwe, 2001:163).

He argued further that dissonance is only a matter of relativity. What an era perceives as dissonant could be tolerable and even taken as consonant in the era after it. What guarantees tolerance and perception in this case becomes the frequency of use of a particular system. In compositional practice, he created a piece entitled, Bata, the third movement in his piano work, Talking drums. In his compositional procedure, he made use of tones derived from the Yoruba Bata ensemble with particular notice of the bata drum and Iyailu and other associated instruments. From these, he generated hexachords which were group of six notes that informed the ordering of his pentatonic structure. The inverted is also given below:

Fig.1 Hexachord inversions in Uzoigwe’s “Talking Drums”

The lower staff provides the inversion of the tones above. For example, A to B on the first segment of the upper staff is inverted to be C to B-flat which is the movement of a tone (two semitones) in opposite directions. Also, the descent from B to E on the upper staff of the first segment is inverted to be B-flat rising to F which gives a perfect fifth interval in both cases but in opposite direction.

Atonality in African Art Music

African art music has two basic obligations: to wisely accommodate the duality of African and Western musical language into a unit form and to conspicuously indicate African musical materials and sonic sensibility. This implies that composers who must successfully compose African Art music must have adequate knowledge of the two musical cultures with preference to African music. This concept of “intercultural creativity” has been discussed by some scholars. (Euba, 1999; Sadoh, 2004; Euba, 2014; Ofuani, 2022).

The combination of both musical cultures does not imply necessarily that a western tonal system comes into dominance. The African musical materials, perhaps the ones gotten from ethnomusicological procedure, can be taken into a western medium—say a piano—but with an ordering, tonal/atonal structure and ambience that is guided more by the African musical sensing. “We may utilize Western technology to reproduce musical tones, but we may not adopt Western tonal and rhythmic perceptions to conceive and order musical patterns” (Uzoigwe, 2001:173).

This kind of mentality will enable African composers decolonize their minds and music while composing. This will enable many African art music composers see African art music as an opportunity to promote African musical consciousness with the western medium only as a clothing and not as a body. This give an advantage of creating the kind of music that the African audience that relate better with and the kind that cultural outsiders will look upon as unique and distinct.

This kind of procedure will most likely lead to producing music that will not pay respect to European tonal system, which European-trained composers will call atonal music. In this case—looking at it from an African-sensed utility product—atonal music will not become a deviation from the normal (the tonal system) but a creation that resonates African’s inherent cultural system and familiarity. The preponderance of European tonal system in African art music especially in the four-part choral style is directly a promotion of European tonal system. This is not to say that some Africans do not enjoy African Art choral music. Rather, the number of adherents in that line and the level of patronage and support shows to which extent we can say it resonates African musical sensibility. While some may argue that art music is for the initiated or an elitist few, they should not forget that the appreciation, propagation, promotion and patronage of an art form stand at the heart of its survival and significance in our fast-changing world. This is not to state that once one is composing atonal African art music, they are decolonizing music or writing something that will definitely become acceptable by Africans. Rather, the idea is that while composing African art music—one that is pointed towards African identity—the insistence on not being pulled by the established European tonal ideals will likely provide room for music that one may consider atonal, not because we do not have examples of what appears like tonal forms in African music, but because we think of those ‘tonal’ forms the way an

African would and not as a westerner. It is the same way that scoring African music gotten from direct African performances, may include quarter-tonal and semitonal disparities when scored or listened to with western notational software and European-trained ears respectively. In fact, there are cases of disparities in the performance of same piece at different times. One can take ideas in this regard from emergence of chance music and aleatory music, serialism and other twentieth century musical kinds as sample of the possibility of music that shows an urge to deviate from the colonizing effects of European music. African art music composers can take courage to begin a journey that is uniquely theirs. While a Western medium or material may be involved, it will be bound to follow the gravitational pull of African-sensed musical creativity and tonal sensibility.

Atonal Art music in a digital era

Music composition and performance has been greatly influenced by digital process. Composing and performing atonal music has a lot to benefit from digital means. African Pop musicians has benefitted immensely from using digital means to compensate from the limitations of live sounds. Being that Atonal music has limitations which borders around producing live sounds, then digital means comes to play. While the need to embrace atonality is germane in this study, the means for adopting it conveniently are equally necessary. Composers can make use of latest versions of Sibelius softwares such as version seven (7), finale softwares, use of midi approach for inputting sounds and use of recording software such as Cubase, Nuendo, FL studio and so on. Some of these softwares has ends that converts to staff notation. This means that the traditional approach to staff notation and its training may be modified. Those who sight-read music will have to be taught to relate with music that is not strictly based on a tonal or key system. It includes that rehearsals and performances may involve digitally recorded sound, space for inclusion of sounds outside the provision of a staff notation and room for improvisations. Beyond this, performers of African art music especially during improvisation should be allowed to make music that are 'Africanly' tolerable without forcing them to sound European both in sound and in technique. Use of digital means for realizing African music has been criticized as having a lot of limitations and impediments to creativity. This is rather an empty excuse as virtually everything in other disciplines is going digital despite shortcomings. The more African composers and performers embrace the digital method, the more they get open to means of solving its contemporary challenges of flowing along with them. It is more important to protect content than contentions. In other words, it is more necessary to protect African identity than to massage the ego of those who feel that digital method of music making is not appealing to them. Digital means provides a broad and less restrictive ground for musical expressive that guarantees freedom of expression of original intent as opposed to the strict use of staff notation and even instruments which are configured to drive one towards European musical sound making. It is also true that unique African sound, scales and non-tonal structures can be configured as templates using digital means. These are sacrifices African composers and performers should be willing to make for African identity to be promoted in their African art music.

CONCLUSION

The use of the term African atonal art music composition and performance in this paper refers to music that is not pulled by the equal-temperament of the European tonal system. This paper addressed the possible use of atonal music, with its expanse of possibilities as a means of creating African art music that largely represents African music creativity and sensibility. It included the approach of Uzoigwe in composing African art atonal music which clearly shows possibilities available to composers. Further, it explains the use of digital method to mitigate the challenges of live actualization of atonal music as well as the wide range of possible manipulations and prospects of having unique sound-spaces that are uniquely African and free from excessive colonial impact.

RECOMMENDATIONS

It is possible through increased awareness and orientation on the insistence of making African art music that is based on African knowledge system, that African composers and performers can tread new parts such as modification and digitalization of indigenous African musical instruments. This is necessary because the instruments provide a tonal configuration in the ears and minds of composers

and performers, deciding what they consider tonal or atonal, tolerable or intolerable, African or not. This means that what may begin as atonal music may end up becoming the standard for tonality through constant use.

Operas can include atonality in opera scenes, harnessing its power to evoke various kinds of emotions and larger sonic possibilities. While tonal music seeks to use modulations and chords of tension to create variety and continuity, atonal music already has the character of esotericism, constant charm, unpredictability and sonic extravagance. Operas with digital means, can beautify their scenes and music with atonal art music that regulates or introduces the needed mood at a particular time.

The increased use of African musical instruments and samples in music teaching will increase the African consciousness that will make the already colonized mind to accommodate (gradually or instantly) the atonal music sound from a digital or live means.

While some European instruments cannot satisfyingly interpret all the nuances of our music, we can make the success greater by not imposing a particular scale on it or adjusting the pitches to fit into our cultured musical sensibility. When we think of dissonance in African music, what informs our thinking? It is more ideal to allow the music speak for itself. Let the culture spell out the idea behind her music. All these partly point to the reason why atonality is largely absent in the repertoire of Nigerian Art music.

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